

Status of some Toxic Heavy Metal Ions in the Upper Reaches of River Ganges

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Three environmentally significant heavy metals, viz. copper, lead and cadmium have been investigated in waters and bed sediments of the river Ganges in a fairly long stretch of 480 km, i.e. from Badrinath to Narora. The prominent mode of transport of Cu^{2+} and Pb^{2+} is envisaged through the particulate phase and that for Cd^{2+} is via the aqueous phase. No distinct man-made source for these metals could be identified. The geochemical source seems to be the main source for their incidence.

Heavy metals enter into the riverine systems from different natural and man-made sources. Heavy metal pollution is not ameliorated by natural phenomena of biochemical decomposition. It is, however, attenuated by adsorption on the suspended load of the river and on subsequent deposition these are kept in dormant condition until remobilised to aqueous phase due to change in pH, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), mineral content and addition of complexing agents from outer sources.

Investigations of heavy metals in water columns as well as in sediments is an integral part of the pollutional study of any river system. Such investigations have already been conducted and reported¹ for almost all the important rivers of the world and of late similar studies have been taken-up in this country as well². As a part of a research project on the pollution modelling of the Upper Ganges Basin, investigations on heavy metal status in the upper reaches of this river were undertaken.

The system under study is the most extensively used river in India in its upper reaches covering a distance of 480 km from Badrinath (along Alkananda to Devprayag) down to Narora (Fig. 1). The first 240 km of the river from Badrinath to Rishikesh is mountaneous and the rest is plain. In the mountaneous stretch the river drains an area with complex rock assemblages which is quite well cited³. The river then flows over the alluvial Indo-Gangetic plain. In the mountaneous region down to Rishikesh the average bed slope is 1 in 67 and mean

annual rate of flow is $850 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The lower stretch from Rishikesh is plain having an average annual rate of flow⁴ $850\text{--}1700 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Round the year, from October to March the river experiences a lean

Fig. 1. The Upper Ganga basin.

flow condition. With the advent of summer, i.e. from April till the onset of monsoon, the melting of ice from higher altitude regions feed the river with ice-melt water and in the monsoon period the river flows upto the brim and the water is found loaded with suspended solids originating from landslide and erosion.

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Copper, an essential element involved in human metabolism is considered to be non toxic up to a level of concentration 1.0 mg dm^{-3} (WHO guideline⁵). Warnick and Bell⁶ considered 0.01–1.7 ppm copper to be toxic to fish and as little as 0.027 ppm is injurious to aquatic insects. The permissible concentrations for irrigation water, are 0.2 ppm on a continuous basis and 9.0 ppm on a short-term basis in fine textured soil⁷. Lead, a non-essential toxic element, enters the human body via inhalation and through the ingestion of contaminated food and water. Lead poisoning results in the problem of anaemia, damage of central nervous system and kidney. WHO guideline value for drinking water is 0.05 mg dm^{-3} . The recommended maximum concentration of lead in irrigation water for continuous use is 5.0 mg dm^{-3} on all soils. Cadmium is a biologically non-essential, non-beneficial element and is recognised to be of high toxic potential. WHO recommend a guideline value for drinking water at 0.005 ppm. The permissible Cd content in irrigation water on a continuous basis is 0.005 ppm and 0.05 ppm on a short-term use for fine textured soil⁸.

Present study takes into account the incidence of three heavy metals (copper, lead and cadmium), their probable source and mode of transport. The prevailing concentration of heavy metals are compared with the recommended limits for drinking and irrigation water and toxicity towards aquatic organ-

isms to reveal the suitability of river water for the uses.

In natural conditions of river water the suspended load and sediments have the important function of buffering the higher metal concentrations by adsorption or precipitation. As such investigations on the sorption characteristics of the sediments have also been undertaken with a view to obtain some valuable information relating to the tolerance of the system to the added heavy metal load. It is worth pointing that the present status report on the monitoring of river provides too many conflicting data while no effort, so far, has been made to study the sediments etc.

Results and Discussion

Some of the physicochemical parameters of river water have direct or indirect influence on the incidence, transport and speciation of the heavy metals. The values of such parameters, viz. pH, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), dissolved and suspended residue of river water under investigation are shown in Table 1. The pH of water was found to be quite alkaline. This reflects a higher concentration of metals in the particulate phase. The ORP values of the river water were found to be in the range around 200 mV indicating no reducing condition in the stretch covered. The range of mean dissolved residue content for the mountaneous part from Badrinath to Rishikesh is $83\text{--}103.9 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$.

TABLE 1—WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS OF THE UPPER GANGES*

Sampling stations	pH		ORP (mV)		COD (mg dm^{-3})		Dissolved residue (mg dm^{-3})		Suspended residue (mg dm^{-3})	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Badrinath	8.05–8.9	8.47	155–275	215	0.30–0.74	0.52	86.0–134.2	105.6	4.5–299	151.7
Nandprayag	8.01–8.55	8.37	177–318	227	0.92–3.72	1.88	86.0–134.2	105.6	4.1–608	95.0
Rudraprayag	7.99–8.56	8.36	122–290	214	0.80–2.60	1.54	61.4–135.2	92.5	1.9–697	11.8
Srinagar	7.87–8.65	8.31	100–270	207	0.80–4.60	1.90	60.0–144.2	91.3	6.8–848	132.7
Devprayag	7.87–8.56	8.29	159–284	228	0.92–2.00	1.44	57.0–99.8	82.4	4.4–1147	184.6
Rishikesh	7.85–8.65	8.42	112–291	209	0.80–2.70	1.85	85.5–151.5	103.9	3.4–858	153.3
Satyanarayana	7.50–8.63	8.31	105–258	201	1.32–6.69	3.50	288–331.9	303.3	11.1–665	121.8
Balawali	7.51–8.70	8.31	119–321	220	2.44–4.00	3.15	106–222.5	146.8	19.8–1244	209.8
Bijnor	7.48–8.67	8.27	185–285	221	2.44–5.76	4.15	110–222.8	165.6	17.0–1189	272.7
Garhmukteswar	8.10–8.65	8.47	156–240	211	1.47–6.27	3.23	101–187.3	148.1	26.8–1152	298.7
Anupshahar	8.20–8.65	8.53	170–272	216	2.09–5.17	3.61	108–213.3	155.2	5.4–1237	375.0
Narora	8.20–8.72	8.57	195–221	196	2.09–4.32	3.19	103.5–192.4	144.2	26.0–1222	288.6

*Range and mean values for 2 years from October to January.

There is no sudden change in this region. Further down at Satyanarayana, there is a sharp increase (300 mg dm^{-3}), probably due to the confluence of highly mineralised tributary song, which carries water from a catchment of lime deposits and rock phosphate. From this station downward the dissolved residue value attains a range 114–167 mg dm^{-3} upto Narora. The dissolved residue values give an approximate idea of inorganic anions like chloride, sulphate, phosphate, bicarbonate etc., which are complexing ligands for heavy metal ions. The high value of dissolved residue at Satyanarayana is reflected in the concentrations of dissolved metal values. The suspended residue content of the river changes appreciably in different seasons and in different regions of the river. The general trend is a fall in high altitude region and further downstream no regular behaviour is observed.

Heavy metals in water column : The average values of the total and dissolved heavy metal concentrations are summarised in Tables 2–4. A

TABLE 2—TOTAL AND DISSOLVED METAL CONCENTRATIONS ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$) IN WATER COLUMN OF THE UPPER GANGES*

Sampling stations	Total and dissolved metal**	
	No. of samples (<i>n</i>)	Mean concn. (\bar{x})
Badrinath	2 (2)	14.0 (5.5)
Nandprayag	21 (18)	14.1 (6.0)
Rudraprayag	18 (18)	11.9 (5.0)
Srinagar	7 (6)	12.2 (6.5)
Devprayag	17 (16)	16.9 (10.2)
Rishikesh	8 (5)	13.1 (5.3)
Satyanarayana	8 (5)	13.3 (5.6)
Balawali	8 (5)	14.3 (6.2)
Bijnor	8 (4)	16.5 (6.5)
Garhmukteswar	8 (5)	19.2 (6.7)
Anupshahar	7 (5)	19.5 (4.3)
Narora	7 (5)	20.2 (8.8)
Basin	121 (93)	18.1 (6.8)

*Mean values for 2 years from October to January.

**Values in parenthesis are for dissolved metals.

typical concentration profile (cadmium) is depicted in Fig. 2. Dissolved copper content shows a more or less constant value throughout the stretch, only with a sharp rise at Devprayag. This high value may be

due to the confluence of the Bhagirathi, the copper content of which was found to be higher than the mean value for the river. A slight lower value at

TABLE 3—TOTAL AND DISSOLVED METAL CONCENTRATIONS ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$) IN WATER COLUMN OF THE UPPER GANGES*

Sampling stations	Total and dissolved metal**	
	No. of samples (<i>n</i>)	Mean concn. (\bar{x})
Badrinath	2 (2)	55.0 (5.0)
Nandprayag	18 (17)	58.0 (22.3)
Rudraprayag	15 (18)	49.3 (30.0)
Srinagar	5 (5)	42.2 (13.9)
Devprayag	14 (15)	41.7 (24.6)
Rishikesh	6 (5)	39.1 (28.8)
Satyanarayana	6 (5)	58.3 (30.1)
Balawali	7 (4)	54.7 (44.1)
Bijnor	7 (4)	77.7 (37.1)
Garhmukteswar	7 (5)	71.9 (44.7)
Anupshahar	7 (5)	78.0 (37.7)
Narora	6 (5)	83.6 (39.0)
Basin	107 (89)	57.4 (27.7)

*Mean values for 2 years from October to January.

**Values in parenthesis are for dissolved metals.

TABLE 4—TOTAL AND DISSOLVED METAL CONCENTRATIONS ($\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$) IN WATER COLUMN OF THE UPPER GANGES*

Sampling stations	Total and dissolved metal**	
	No. of samples (<i>n</i>)	Mean concn. (\bar{x})
Badrinath	2 (2)	0 (0)
Nandprayag	21 (18)	7.5 (4.5)
Rudraprayag	18 (15)	4.2 (2.5)
Srinagar	7 (6)	9.6 (7.1)
Devprayag	17 (15)	5.6 (4.4)
Rishikesh	8 (5)	5.5 (4.6)
Satyanarayana	8 (4)	8.5 (7.2)
Balawali	8 (4)	16.1 (7.5)
Bijnor	8 (4)	6.1 (4.1)
Garhmukteswar	8 (5)	10.0 (4.2)
Anupshahar	8 (5)	6.1 (4.4)
Narora	8 (5)	17.0 (9.2)
Basin	128 (93)	8.2 (4.8)

*Mean values for 2 years from October to January.

**Values in parenthesis are for dissolved metals.

Anupshahar was observed which may be due to enhanced sorption by the fine grained suspended sediments.

The total copper content in the mountaneous portion of the stretch shows a high value (excluding the valley of Srinagar) and this may be attributed to the higher copper content of the Bhagirathi. From

values of total and dissolved metal are found to be 8.24 and 4.8 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ respectively. Slight higher values than the recommended limit for drinking water are observed for dissolved Cd content at stations like Srinagar, Satyanarayana, Balawali and Narora. More detailed studies in this direction are in progress.

Fig. 2. Cadmium profile for the Upper Ganges (Badrinath to Narora).

Rishikesh to Narora there is a gradual marginal increase and this may be attributed to gradual increase in the suspended load. The concentrations do not exceed the maximum guideline value³ for drinking water and it is also found safe for irrigation.

The dissolved lead content in this stretch of the river is in the range 5.0–44.7 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$ and this too does not exceed the potable limit. The total lead content (in particulate plus aqueous phase) however shows a higher range of concentration varying from 39.15–83.66 $\mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$.

The total and dissolved cadmium content of the stretch presents a similar profile. The basin mean

Extraction of heavy metals in bed sediments : The extractable heavy metal contents of the bed sediments (unsieved and sieved) of different sampling stations are shown in Table 5. The average shale values are as follows : Cu = 45.0; Cd = 0.3; Pb = 20.0 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$. A comparison of the basin mean values with the shale standard indicates the enrichment of Pb and Cd in the basin.

Mode of transport : The percentage of total metal concentrations transported by particulate material observed for different sampling stations are shown in Table 6. From the data it may be concluded that the prominent mode of metal transport in the river is via the particulate phase in case of Cu and Pb, and Cd is transported via the dissolved phase.

Conclusion : The three heavy metals investigated were found to be present in water as well as in bed sediments of the river Ganges. At present, there is no mining and smelting activity along the stretch of the river under consideration. Not a single industry based on these metals is located in this region. Consequently the scope of industrial pollution may be ruled out and the most probable

TABLE 5—MEAN CONCENTRATIONS OF HEAVY METALS IN THE GANGES SEDIMENTS

Station	Metal in unsieved sediment ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)			Metal in sieved (< 63 m) sediment ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		
	Cu	Pb	Cd	Cu	Pb	Cd
Rudraprayag	14.2	23.7	1.5	164.0	106.0	18.0
Kaudiyala	17.9	32.1	2.2	129.6	138.0	0.4
Muni-ki-reti	16.6	22.5	3.7	47.4	176.5	9.6
Balawali	7.3	23.5	3.3	32.2	198.2	2.9
Garhmukteswar	4.1	28.2	2.8	26.0	231.0	2.2
Anupshahar	11.0	31.8	3.4	19.6	84.0	5.8
Narora	4.5	12.2	0.8	15.5	228.0	3.9
Mean (Basin)	10.8	25.5	2.5	49.5	169.6	6.0

source for the incidence of these metals in the river Ganges is only geochemical one.

TABLE 6—PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL METAL TRANSPORTED BY PARTICULATE MATERIAL IN THE GANGES WATER*

Sampling stations	% Cu	% Pb	% Cd
Badrinath	60.7	95.6	—
Nandprayag	56.9	61.5	39.5
Rudraprayag	57.5	39.8	40.1
Srinagar	46.2	67.0	26.1
Devprayag	39.7	41.1	22.3
Rishikesh	59.7	26.4	16.3
Satyanarayana	58.0	75.8	15.3
Balawali	33.7	19.4	53.4
Bijnor	60.6	52.2	32.6
Garhmukteswar	65.2	37.8	58.0
Anupshahar	77.9	51.7	45.8
Narora	56.4	53.3	45.8
Mean value	56.0	51.8	34.4

*Average value for 12 sampling stations.

Experimental

Sampling was done at twelve sampling stations, covering the whole stretch (Badrinath to Narora). The sampling stations (Fig. 1) are at the heights of 3086, 880, 727, 570, 500, 348, 320, 230, 210, 195, 180 and 176 m. Water samples were collected in two months frequency from October to January. Bed sediment samples were collected from seven sampling stations, viz. Rudraprayag, Kaudiyala, Muni-ki-reti, Balawali, Garhmukteswar, Anupshahar and Narora.

Physicochemical parameters, like temperature, pH, ORP, dissolved and suspended residue etc. were determined in addition to the dissolved and total metal content. In the bed sediment and extractable ($\text{HNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ extraction), heavy metal contents were determined using the whole sediments and also the silt and clay fraction ($< 63 \mu\text{m}$).

Grab samples were collected in the stations of the mountaneous region where the river is flushy resulting in well mixed condition, but the approachability is limited. In the sampling stations of the plain region integrated samples were taken for analysis.

The physicochemical parameters were determined following the procedures recommended in the standard methods for analysis of water and waste water⁹. Temperature, pH, conductivity and

ORP were determined on the spot using a portable kit. Water samples for detection of total metal were collected in polythene bottles and concentrated HNO_3 was added on the spot to bring pH of the sample below 2. The samples were digested with concentrated HNO_3 and pre-concentrated by evaporation. The samples were filtered with $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ membrane, pre-concentrated by evaporation and utilised for the detection of dissolved metal contents. The sediment samples were collected from the river bed from shallow water nearer to the bank. These were air-dried and sieved. The unsieved and the sieved sample ($< 63 \mu\text{m}$) were utilised for $\text{HNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$ extraction¹⁰.

The metals were estimated using an IL-751 atomic absorption spectrophotometer using air-acetylene flame.

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